

Influence of Family Structure on Secondary School Students Attitudes towards Marriage and Divorce Concepts in Egor, Edo State, Nigeria

Bazuaye, Joy Omoze¹

Omo.bazuaye@uniben.edu

08055255821

&

Aghahowa, Bernice Nefeye²

bernice.emwanta@uniben.edu

07038976781

¹Faculty of Education, University of Benin, Nigeria.

Abstract

This study examines the influence of different family structures on secondary school students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria. The study explores how family structure shape secondary school student's perceptions of marriage stability and the acceptability of divorce. Two research questions were raised to guide the study, and they were hypothesized at a 0.05 level of significance. A survey research design was employed, with 380 Junior Secondary School 3 (JSS 3) students selected from six public schools through a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire validated by three experts in Social Studies and Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Benin. The instrument demonstrated acceptable reliability, yielding Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.74 for the marriage attitude scale and 0.70 for the divorce attitude scale. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, and Least Significant Difference (LSD) post-hoc tests. Results indicate significant differences in students' attitudes based on family structure. Students from monogamous families exhibited more positive views on marriage and a more conservative stance on divorce, whereas students from single-parent households displayed more critical perspectives on marriage and a higher acceptance of divorce. The findings highlight the critical role of family structure in shaping young people's attitudes toward marriage and divorce, with implications for educational policies, counseling interventions, and family support programs. The study recommends integrating family dynamics education into school curricula, providing tailored counseling services, establishing mentorship programs, fostering school-parent collaboration, and conducting further research to better understand and address the impact of family type on students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce.

Keywords: Family type, marriage, divorce, Social Studies, secondary school students

Introduction

Social Studies is a multidisciplinary subject taught in schools to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to address personal, social, and civic challenges both within and beyond the classroom. Social Studies education in Nigeria is designed to instill positive social values, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills in students, thereby preparing them for effective citizenship (Nwalado & Obro 2020). The subject underscores the family as the fundamental unit of society, shaping students' attitudes toward socio-cultural issues including marriage and divorce. Given the diverse family structures in Nigeria the way students perceive and internalize these concepts maybe significantly influenced by their diverse family backgrounds. Among the many themes embedded in the Social Studies curriculum are marriage and divorce, concepts integral to societal functioning. These topics aim not only to prepare junior secondary school students for academic success in internal and external examinations, such as the NECO Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE), but also to foster critical thinking about family dynamics and their broader social implications. According to Arnett (2000) young adulthood is an important period when individuals begin to explore intimacy and sexuality, as well as to test the assumptions or attitudes they might hold regarding romantic relationships. Despite the importance of the concept of marriage and divorce, chief examiners' reports from the 2018 and 2022 NECO BECE in Social Studies have highlighted persistent poor student performance in questions related to marriage and divorce suggesting a possible gap in students' understanding of these concepts. While teaching methods are often blamed for low performance, family background may play a more significant role in shaping students' preconceived notions about marriage and divorce.

In Nigeria, societal expectations surrounding marriage remain strong, yet family structures and background are increasingly diverse. These variations may influence how adolescents perceive the desirability, stability, and permanence of marriage, as well as their acceptance of divorce as a solution to marital instability. Family background, encompassing social,

economic, and cultural characteristics, has long been recognized as a critical factor influencing students' learning experiences and perspectives. Studies in Nigeria have demonstrated that family background plays a role in shaping students' learning experiences in Social Studies. For instance, a study by Eke (2022) found that family background significantly influences pupils' academic performance in Enugu East Local Government Area, highlighting the role of parental education and socioeconomic status. Family structure, whether monogamous, polygamous, or single-parenting, could also impact children's development. Research indicates that children from stable family environments tend to perform better academically. For example, a study by Mustapha and Odediran (2018) examined the impact of parental separation on the self-esteem of in-school adolescents in Ilorin, Nigeria, revealing that parental separation adversely affects adolescents' self-esteem, which can, in turn, influence their academic performance.

Marriage and divorce are integral components of social structures that shape the upbringing and worldview of individuals, particularly young people (Jensen, Willoughby, Holman, Busby & Shafer, 2014). Existing literature on marriage formation and dissolution highlights key environmental factors—rather than individual traits—that influence children's perspectives. These include the number of family transitions they experience, such as parental remarriage (Kelly & Emery, 2003), the degree of conflict in their parents' marriage (Cui & Fincham, 2010), and being raised in a single-parent household (Valle & Tillman, 2014). These factors align with social learning theories, which suggest that children develop attitudes toward marriage by observing their parents' relationships and growing up within particular family structures and social norms (Li, 2014).

Monogamous family structures, often characterized by stability and exclusivity, tend to provide children with consistent role models, fostering positive attitudes toward marriage. Studies suggest that students from monogamous homes are more likely to value marital commitment and view divorce as a last resort. According to Yu and Adler-Baeder (2007) young adults from intact families hold significantly more positive attitudes toward marriage than children of divorce, although the significance remains small and might not be meaningful. Furthermore, the studies show a robust, yet non-linear association between parental divorce and more favourable attitudes toward divorce, with young adults from divorced families being three times more likely to think positively about divorce than young adults from intact families (Amato 2000, Ogunleye, 2014). Also, polygamous families, which remain prevalent in some Nigerian communities, expose students to a different marital framework, where multiple spousal relationships may normalize marital conflicts and hierarchies within the household. Students from polygamous backgrounds may develop mixed perceptions of marriage—while some embrace polygamy as a cultural norm, others may view it as a source of familial instability that could affect their future marital expectations. According to a study by Bahari et al. (2021), women in polygamous marriages are more likely to experience depression, while children from such families also display higher levels of psychological distress compared to those in monogamous marriages. Also, Al-Krenawi and Graham (2012) found that women in polygamous marriages report higher psychological distress and lower levels of marital and life satisfaction compared to those in monogamous marriages within the Bedouin-Arab community.

Single-parent families, whether resulting from divorce, being pregnant out of wedlock, separation, or the death of a spouse, present unique challenges that could shape students' perspectives on marriage and divorce. While many children from single-parents families exhibit similar overall functioning to their peers from intact families (Kelly & Emery, 2003), research suggests they may experience delayed or " sleeper " effects, which manifest later in life, particularly when they enter romantic relationships and establish their own families (Li, 2014). Students raised by single-parents may experience economic and emotional hardships, which can either strengthen their resolve to pursue stable marriages or lead to skepticism about marital longevity. The absence of one parent may also impact their emotional development and ability to navigate relationships effectively. According to Valle and Tillman (2014), children from single-parent families after divorce are more likely to cohabitate and never marry as adults,

However, the interplay between classroom instruction and family influences can be complex. Adolescents from families that experience instability or marital discord may not perceive marriage and divorce as abstract academic concepts but rather as deeply personal and emotional realities. This intersection underscores the need for research that examines how family type influences students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce. The changing structure of families in Nigeria, particularly in recently turned urban regions such as Egor LGA, has become a focus of academic attention. Studies (Ekpenyong & Udis, 2016) have revealed a significant rise in single-parent families, driven by factors such as urbanization, economic challenges, and evolving societal norms). These shifts have implications for adolescents' attitudes toward the stability and desirability of marriage and their acceptance of divorce as a legitimate resolution to marital conflict.

Research has shown that various family structures influence young individuals' perceptions of marriage and divorce. Al-Krenawi and Graham (2006) found that women in polygamous marriages reported lower marital satisfaction and mental health outcomes compared to those in monogamous marriages, suggesting that family stability plays a crucial role in shaping

attitudes toward relationships. Similarly, Bahari, Norhayati, and Nik Hazlina (2021) conducted a systematic review highlighting the psychological impact of polygamous marriage on women and children, noting that children in such environments often develop mixed attitudes toward marriage due to the complexities of family dynamics. Furthermore, Wolfinger (2005) explored the intergenerational transmission of divorce, concluding that children of divorced parents are more likely to experience marital instability themselves. This supports the notion that exposure to family disruption influences one's expectations and attitudes toward marriage. Additionally, Yu and Adler-Baeder (2007) emphasized the role of parental remarriage quality in shaping young adults' perceptions of relationships, demonstrating that positive remarriage experiences can counteract the negative effects of divorce. These studies collectively reinforce the idea that family background, including monogamous, polygamous, and single-parent structures, significantly impacts students' perspectives on marriage and divorce.

This study seeks to build on existing findings by exploring the influence of different family structure—such as monogamous, polygamous and single-parent families, on the attitudes of secondary school students towards marriage as a social institution in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. This research aims to provide comprehensive insights that could inform educational and social policies aimed at fostering healthy family relationships and guiding youth development in the region. The findings will also contribute to the existing literature on family dynamics and youth perspectives, offering valuable implications for educators, policymakers, and community leaders.

The traditional structure of the family, long regarded as a cornerstone of societal stability, is undergoing significant transformation, particularly in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. With the rise of various family forms, including single-parent households, monogamous and polygamous family arrangements, there is growing concern about how these changes influence the attitudes of young people towards marriage and divorce. Adolescents, who are in a critical stage of developing their values and beliefs, are likely to be significantly influenced by the type of family in which they are raised. This shift raises important questions about the potential impact on their future relationships, their perceptions of the permanence and sanctity of marriage, and their openness to or apprehension about divorce. Existing research has documented varying attitudes towards marriage and divorce among young people, often linked to their family backgrounds. However, there is a noticeable gap in the literatures regarding how these dynamics play out within the specific socio-cultural context of Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, an area characterized by a mix of traditional values and modern influences. Understanding these attitudes is crucial, not only for predicting future trends in marriage and divorce but also for informing interventions aimed at promoting healthy family relationships.

Therefore, the problem this study seeks to address is the inadequate comprehensive understanding of how different family structure influence secondary school students' attitudes towards marriage and divorce in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. This knowledge will be beneficial to educators, policymakers, and community leaders in addressing the evolving needs of young people in this area and beyond, potentially leading to increased marital stability and lower incidence of divorce in the future. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the specific ways in which family structure affects students' attitudes, thereby providing insights that can guide efforts to foster positive attitudes towards marriage and reduce the likelihood of divorce among the next generation.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the influence of family structure (monogamous, polygamous, and single-parent) on secondary school students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Determine whether there is a difference in students' attitudes toward marriage based on their family structure in Egor LGA.
2. Examine whether there is a difference in students' attitudes toward divorce based on their family structure in Egor LGA.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. Is there any difference in the students' attitude towards marriage based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA?
2. Is there any difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA?

Hypotheses

Research questions 1-2 were hypothesized and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the students' attitude towards marriage based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the students’ attitude towards divorce based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. This design was appropriate because it allows for the systematic collection and analysis of data to describe and compare students’ attitude towards marriage and divorce based on their family structure. The population of this study comprised all Junior Secondary School 3 (JSS 3) students in Egor LGA, Edo State, totaling 7,674 students across twelve public junior secondary schools (Edo State Ministry of Education, 2023). The sample size for this study consisted of 380 Junior Secondary School (JSS 3) students selected from selected public junior secondary schools in the LGA. The sample size of 380 students was determined using Yamane’s formula (Yamane, 1967) based on a population of 7,674 JSS 3 students in Egor LGA with a 5% margin of error. This ensures a 95% confidence level, enhancing reliability and minimizing sampling error. The sample size is adequate for One-Way ANOVA and LSD Post-Hoc tests, allowing meaningful comparisons across family structures. It also improves representativeness, ensuring a more accurate analysis of students’ attitudes toward marriage and divorce while aligning with best practices in social science research. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed in selecting the study sample. First, the Local Government Area was categorized into six districts: Ugbowo, Evbuotubu, Uselu, Ogida, Okhoro, and Ekenhuan. Next, one school was randomly selected from each of these districts, resulting in a total of six schools. Finally, students were randomly chosen from the selected schools, with sixty (60) students drawn from four schools and seventy (70) students selected from two schools, bringing the total sample size to 380.

A structured questionnaire titled "Family Structure and Students’ Attitude towards Marriage and Divorce (FSSAMD)" was used for data collection. The questionnaire had two sections: Section A: Demographic information and Section B: Items assessing students’ attitudes toward marriage and divorce using a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree). The instrument was validated by three experts in Social Studies and Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Benin. The reliability was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.74 (Marriage attitude scale) and 0.70 (Divorce attitude scale). These values indicate acceptable reliability for the study.

The questionnaire was administered with the assistance of two trained research assistants. Students were assured of confidentiality and voluntary participation. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive Statistics -Mean, Standard Deviation, One-way ANOVA (to test differences in attitudes based on family type) and LSD Post Hoc Test (to determine where significant differences lie) at an alpha level for significance: 0.05

Results

Research question 1: Is there any difference in the students’ attitude towards marriage based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Difference in the Students’ Attitude towards Marriage Based on their Family Structure

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Monogamy	62.7917	4.84360
Polygamy	61.7143	8.14588
single-parent	58.5000	5.06720
Total	62.1111	5.90700

The Table showed the descriptive statistics on difference in the students’ attitude towards marriage based on their family structure. It was observed that the respondents in monogamy had mean of 62.79, those in polygamy had mean of 61.71 and those in single-parent family structure had mean of 58.50.

Research question 2: Is there a significant difference in the students’ attitude towards divorce based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Difference in the Students' Attitude towards Divorce Based on their Family Structure

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Monogamy	37.7417	4.55498
Polygamy	37.5714	3.91459
single-parent	33.8333	4.34200
Total	37.3111	4.52218

The Table showed the descriptive statistics on difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure. It was observed that the respondents in monogamous families had a mean of 37.74, those in polygamous families had a mean of 37.57 and those in single-parent family structure had mean of 33.83.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the students' attitude towards marriage based on their family structure (monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA.

Table 3: One way ANOVA for Difference in the Students' Attitude towards Marriage Based on their Family Structure ANOVA

Attitude Marriage					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	296.915	2	148.457	4.417	.013
Within Groups	5948.863	199	33.609		
Total	6245.778	201			

The Table indicated one way ANOVA for difference in the students' attitude towards marriage based on their family structure. The examination revealed an f-value of 4.41 with a significance level of 0.01, which is below the predetermined alpha level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant difference in students' attitudes toward marriage based on their family structure, is dismissed. This indicates a noteworthy difference in students' attitudes toward marriage based on their family structure, suggesting an influence of the family structure on students' attitude towards marriage.

Table 4: LSD Post-Hoc

(I) family_structure	(J) family_structure	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Monogamy	Polygamy	1.07738	1.03938	.301
	single-parent	4.29167	1.46536	.004
Polygamy	Monogamy	-1.07738	1.03938	.301
	single-parent	3.21429	1.63322	.051
single-parent	Monogamy	-4.29167	1.46536	.004
	Polygamy	-3.21429	1.63322	.051

The LSD post-hoc indicated where the significant difference lies across the family structure. It was observed that there were significant differences between monogamy (nuclear) group and single-parenting family structure (mean difference=4.29). The results show that family structure has a significant impact on the measured variable. Specifically, there is a statistically significant difference between monogamous and single-parent families ($p = 0.004$), suggesting a meaningful distinction between these two-family types.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure (e.g., monogamous, polygamous and single-parent) in Egor LGA.

Table 5: One way ANOVA for difference in the Students' Attitude towards Divorce Based on their Family Structure ANOVA

attitude_divorce					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	242.800	2	121.400	6.287	.002
Within Groups	3417.777	199	19.309		
Total	3660.578	201			

The Table indicated one way ANOVA for difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure. It was observed that the f-value is 6.28 and the level of significance is 0.00 which is less than the set alpha level of

0.05. Thus the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure is rejected. This shows that there is significant difference in the students' attitude towards divorce based on their family structure.

Table 6: LSD post hoc

(I) family_type	(J) family_type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Monogamy	Polygamy	.17024	.78782	.829
	single-parent	3.90833	1.11070	.001
Polygamy	Monogamy	-.17024	.78782	.829
	single-parent	3.73810	1.23794	.003
single-parent	Monogamy	-3.90833	1.11070	.001
	Polygamy	-3.73810	1.23794	.003

The LSD post hoc indicated where the significant different lies across the family structure. It was observed that there were significant differences between monogamous and single-parenting family structure (mean difference=3.90) and polygamous and single-parent family structure (mean difference= 3.73). There is a significant difference between single-parent families and both monogamous and polygamous families, with individuals from single-parent families exhibiting distinct attitudes or behaviors. However, there is no significant difference between monogamous and polygamous families ($p = 0.829$), suggesting these two family structures are similar in the context of this study

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals that family structure significantly influences secondary school students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce. Students from monogamous families exhibit the most positive outlook on marriage, followed by those from polygamous families, while students from single-parent households display the most cautious or skeptical views. This pattern aligns with previous research demonstrating that family background plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' perceptions of marriage and divorce (Li & Brown, 2019).

The study's findings suggest that students from monogamous families are more likely to hold positive attitudes toward marriage, which can be attributed to the stability and consistent parental role models within such households. This is supported by Kalmijn (2015), who found that individuals from intact families tend to have stronger marital commitments due to the stability experienced during childhood. Similarly, Lansford (2018) highlights how cultural differences in parental divorce affect children's long-term attitudes toward marriage, reinforcing the idea that stable family environments contribute to more favorable views on marriage.

In contrast, students from single-parent families tend to be more skeptical about marriage, likely due to their direct experiences of parental separation, financial difficulties, and emotional strain. These experiences may lead to a more critical stance on marriage, similar to the observations made by Wolfinger, Kowaleski-Jones, and Smith (2019), who found that individuals from unstable family backgrounds tend to develop more liberal attitudes toward marriage and divorce. Additionally, the findings resonate with Fingerman, Huo, and Birditt (2020), who emphasize the importance of intergenerational relationships in shaping attitudes toward marriage.

The study also indicates that students from single-parent families are more accepting of divorce than their peers from monogamous or polygamous families. This finding is corroborated by Li (2014) whose study suggests that children from single-parent families may have a higher likelihood of viewing divorce as an acceptable solution, influenced by the normalization of divorce within their own homes. Exposure to parental separation may normalize divorce as a viable option rather than a societal failure. This aligns with research by Vanassche, Swicegood, and Matthijs (2015), who found that attitudes toward divorce are shaped by social contexts and family experiences. Similarly, Bahari et al. (2021) discuss the psychological impact of polygamous marriages on children, highlighting the emotional challenges that may contribute to their perceptions of marital stability and divorce.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that family structure significantly shapes secondary school students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce in Egor LGA, Edo State, Nigeria. Students from monogamous families generally hold more favorable views of marriage and more conservative attitudes toward divorce, reflecting the stability and consistent parental role modeling

associated with this family type. In contrast, students from single-parent households tend to adopt a more critical stance on marriage and a greater acceptance of divorce, likely influenced by their experiences of parental separation, financial strain, or emotional instability.

These variations in attitudes suggest that students internalize perspectives on marriage and divorce based on the relational dynamics they observe within their households. The relative stability of monogamous families appears to reinforce traditional marital ideals, while the challenges associated with single-parenting may contribute to more pragmatic or cautious views. Similarly, students from polygamous families exhibit mixed perceptions, potentially shaped by exposure to complex family hierarchies and varying marital relationships. Overall, the findings underscore the profound role of family background in shaping young people's expectations and beliefs about marriage and divorce, which may have lasting implications for their future relationships and decision-making.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the influence of family structure on students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce.

1. Schools should incorporate comprehensive lessons on family structures, marriage, and divorce into their curricula to equip students with a well-rounded understanding of these concepts. This approach will enable students to critically analyze their attitudes toward marriage and divorce, fostering informed decision-making irrespective of their family background.
2. Schools should establish specialized counseling programs that address the unique emotional and psychological challenges faced by students from single-parent and polygamous households. Providing professional support will help these students navigate their perceptions of marriage and relationships in a healthy and constructive manner.
3. Schools should work closely with parents and guardians to promote open discussions on marriage, family values, and relationship dynamics. Organizing family-focused educational programs can encourage parents to create supportive home environments, model healthy relationships, and foster constructive conversations with their children.
4. Policymakers should develop and implement family welfare initiatives that support single-parent and polygamous households in providing stable and nurturing environments for children. Educational institutions can advocate for such policies to reduce the adverse effects of family instability on students' attitudes.
5. More extensive research is needed to explore the long-term effects of family structure on students' attitudes toward marriage and divorce. Future studies should investigate how these attitudes evolve over time and influence students' relationship choices, providing data-driven insights for improved educational policies and family-oriented support systems.

References

- Al-Krenawi, A. & Graham, J. R. (2006). A comparison of family functioning, life and marital satisfaction, and mental health of women in polygamous and monogamous marriages. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 52(1), 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640060061245>
- Amato, P. R. (2000). The consequences of divorce for adults and children: An update. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 62(5), 1269–1287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3737.2000.01269.x>
- Arnett, J. J. (2000). Emerging adulthood: A theory of development from the late teens through the twenties. *American Psychologist*, 55(5), 469–480. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.5.469>
- Bahari, S. I., Norhayati, M. N., Nik Hazlina, N. H., et al. (2021). Psychological impact of polygamous marriage on women and children: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 21, 823. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-04301-7>
- Cui, M., Wickrama, K. A. S., Lorenz, F. O. & Conger, R. D. (2011). Linking parental divorce and marital discord to the timing of emerging adults' marriage and cohabitation. In F. D. Fincham & M. Cui (Eds.), *Romantic relationships in emerging adulthood* (pp. 123–141). Cambridge University Press.
- Eke, F. O. (2022). Family background and pupils' academic performance in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. *Godfrey Okoye University Institutional Repository*. Retrieved from <https://repository.gou.edu.ng>
- Ekpenyong, N. S. & Udis, L. (2016). Single-parent families and their impact on children: A study of Amassoma community in Bayelsa State. *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 4(9), 1-10. <https://www.idpublications.org>
- Fingerman, K. L., Huo, M. & Birditt, K. S. (2020). A decade of research on intergenerational ties: Progress and future directions. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 82(1), 383-405. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12617>

- Jensen, T. M., Willoughby, B. J., Holman, T. B., Busby, D. M. & Shafer, K. (2014). Associations between family and interpersonal processes and emerging adult marital paradigms: Does adult attachment mediate? *Journal of Adult Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10804-014-9200-3>
- Kalmijn, M. (2015). Family disruption and attitudes toward divorce in adulthood. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 77(4), 924-940. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12192>
- Kelly, J. B. & Emery, R. E. (2003). Children's adjustment following divorce: Risk and resilience perspectives. *Family Relations*, 52(4), 352–362. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3729.2003.00352.x>
- Lansford, J. E. (2018). Parental divorce and children's adjustment: Understanding variability across cultures. *Journal of Family Studies*, 24(1), 67-84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13229400.2016.1262583>
- Li, J. & Brown, S. L. (2019). Family structure and attitudes toward marriage: Evidence from cross-national studies. *Social Science Research*, 83, 102314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2019.102314>
- Li, X. (2014). What influences the attitudes of people in the United States toward marriage? A critical review. *The Family Journal: Counseling and Therapy for Couples and Families*, 22(3), 292–297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/066480714529743>
- Mustapha, M. & Odediran, A. (2018). The impact of parental separation on the self-esteem of in-school adolescents in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Review*, 13(4), 87–102. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1201337.pdf>
- Nwalado, J. N. & Obro, S. (2020). Role of social studies education in national development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 4(12), 1-5.
- Ogunleye, A. J. (2014). Effect of parental conflict and divorce/separation on children's attitude towards marriage in Nigeria. *Journal of Culture, Society and Development*, 4, 57–60.
- Vanassche, S., Swicegood, G. & Matthijs, K. (2015). Marriage and divorce in a cross-national perspective: The role of social context. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 46(4), 537-555. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jcfs.46.4.537>
- Wolfinger, N. H., Kowaleski-Jones, L. & Smith, K. R. (2019). Family instability and attitudes toward divorce. *Journal of Family Theory & Review*, 11(2), 286-304. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jftr.12350>
- Yu, T. & Adler-Baeder, F. (2007). The intergenerational transmission of relationship quality: The effects of parental remarriage quality on young adults' relationships. *Journal of Divorce & Remarriage*, 47(3-4), 87–102. https://doi.org/10.1300/J087v47n03_05